

THE IMPORTANCE OF SPEAKING SKILLS IN ENGLISH CLASSROOMS

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Abstract

In this globalization era, there have been drastic changes taking place all over the world. These tremendous vicissitudes occur when people have a strong desire to achieve something. People's desires are fulfilled when they clearly express their ideas and opinions with others. Thus, they need to learn communication skills in order to fulfill their ambitions, desires, and goals. In this modern world, communication skills play a vital role and one must have mastery over these skills to get success in their respective fields. So, speaking is the most important skill among all the four language skills in order to communicate well in this global world. As English is widely used all over the world, there is a need for learners to acquire the communication skills of it to get success in their respective fields. Thus, the classroom is the ideal platform to acquire good communication skills, especially, speaking skills. The teachers have to understand the problems of the ELLs (English language learners) and try to implement various teaching strategies in their classrooms in order to develop their learners' speaking skills in English classrooms. This is possible for the teachers when they change their methods and

materials and by using the latest techniques of teaching speaking skills. Therefore, the teachers should introduce some group and pair activities in their regular English classrooms that the ELLs can develop their speaking skills enormously. This paper sheds light on the importance of speaking skills in English classrooms. First of all, this paper discloses the significance of the basic language skills of English. Later, this paper also explains the importance of speaking skills in English classrooms in a comprehensive way. It also explains the need to teach speaking skills. Then the kinds of speaking situations and the main advantages of speaking skills are explained elaborately. Furthermore, this paper also supplies several techniques to develop speaking skills among the EFL/ESL learners in the English classrooms. Finally, this paper suggests some useful tips for the teachers to introduce various activities that involve the ELLs more on practicing their speaking skills in English classrooms. Moreover, it also suggests the ELLs improve their speaking skills as these are very useful for them to build their future career in a perfect way.

Keywords: activities; communication; English classrooms; ELLs; speaking skills; strategies

Introduction

The Importance of the English Language In these modern days, the whole world has become a global village and people communicate with each other in a common language, i.e. English. The English language is spoken all over the world and it has attained the status of the global language. English is the language widely used in

the field of scientific research, education, business, the internet, travel and tourism, media and newspapers, software, medicine, engineering, information and technology, entertainment, banking and so on. English is the language that is used mostly for business correspondence and internet purposes. It is the only major language used in writing scientific research articles as more than 85% of the research publications are in English. It is the international language used for trade and commerce. Even in the IT field also, most of the programmes are written in English and even they communicate with their colleagues or other software professionals those who work around the world in English. Furthermore, most of the books related to higher education are published in English. Due to several advantages of English, many people are learning the English language to attain fruitful results in their respective fields.

The Basic Language Skills of English

As English serves the purpose of international communication, most of the foreign language learners try to learn it. In this process, they have to acquire all the four basic skills of the language, viz. listening, speaking, reading and writing. Listening and reading are passive skills or receptive skills, whereas, speaking and writing are active skills or productive skills.

Listening and reading are considered to be passive or receptive skills as the learners do not show their talent in exhibiting these skills. They just listen to the language or read it without producing anything. Whereas, the learners have to produce sentences on their own and they need a lot of practice and learn many things related to grammar, vocabulary, sentence structure and usage. Therefore, speaking and writing are considered to be active or productive skills.

The Importance of Speaking Skills

In the present global world, communication plays a vital role in getting success in all fields. Language is used as a tool for communication. Perfect communication is not possible for people without using a language. Moreover, people cannot achieve their aims, objectives, and goals without using proper language to communicate. Therefore, there is a need for a language to communicate with others those who live all around the globe. As English is considered the international language and it is spoken all over the world, it serves the purpose of communicating with the people who live in different regions, states, countries, and continents of the world.

Speaking skill is the most important skill to acquire foreign or second language learning. Among the four key language skills, speaking is deemed to be the most important skill in learning a foreign or second language. Brown and Yuke (1983) say, “Speaking is the skill that the students will be judged upon most in real life situations”. Regardless of its importance, teaching speaking skills have been undervalued and most of the EFL/ESL teachers have been continuing their teaching of speaking skills just as memorization of dialogues or repetition of drills. Nevertheless, the modern world demands for the requirement of communication skills for the learners and the English teachers have to teach the ELLs the needed skills so that they will improve their abilities in speaking and perform well in real-life situations. In the present EFL/ESL teaching environment, oral skills are completely neglected whereas employability depends more on communication than technology. As very less priority has been given to the important elements of language such as phonological, morphological, semantic and syntactic aspects, it has become a major impediment for the ELLs to acquire the speaking skills among

the learners of English. So far, more concentration has been given to reading and writing skills. After realizing the importance of oral communication skills, more emphasis is now laid on developing the speaking skills of the learners to pursue their studies successfully and excel in their fields once they finish their education. Moreover, English is the language of getting opportunities for employment and getting success to achieve the desired goals in life. According to Bueno, Madrid, and McLaren (2006: 321), “Speaking is one of the most difficult skills language learners have to face. Speaking is considered the most important of the four language skills of English. Even the learners learn the language for so many years; they find it difficult to speak in real time situations when it is demanded. There are many reasons to overcome this. First of all, the ELLs should understand the importance of speaking skills and try to acquire them as they need them to compete in this competitive world.

Among the four basic skills of the English language, speaking seems to be difficult because the speakers have to produce sentences on the spur of the moment. It is quite difficult for foreign or second language learners to produce sentences without learning the grammatical structures and having proper knowledge of adequate vocabulary. Therefore, the English language learners of EFL/ESL face many problems in speaking grammatical sentences in English. Since speaking skills play a dominant role in communication, people try to learn these skills in order to communicate well with the entire community all around the world.

Why are Speaking Skills taught in English classrooms?

In this global world, there is a need to share our ideas and thoughts with the people who live around the world in order to fulfill our desires and deeds. This is a

competitive world and each and every English language learner wants to improve his/her speaking skills to sustain in this global market. Moreover, most of the selections in getting jobs depend on the communication skills of the individuals, especially, their speaking skills. The interviewers also recognize the talent of the individuals in the form of speaking skills within a short period of time. The job seekers those who can prove their skills at that particular moment will be occupying the best places in their career. Moreover, these speaking skills are also useful for professionals to develop their career. In addition to this, these speaking skills are more useful for the employees those who are working in business organizations to promote their businesses. It is also a known fact that excellent, outstanding and inspiring speakers highly motivate and win the hearts of the audience. As speaking skills play a vital role in many aspects, there is a need for EFL/ESL learners to concentrate more on them. Furthermore, the teachers are advised to implement several useful strategies in their classrooms in order to involve the learners more on learning speaking skills in their English classrooms.

The Advantages of Speaking Skills Even if there are four other skills in the English language, speaking skills are the most effective one among them as a majority of communication is done through speech. Therefore, speaking skills are the most important method of communication. There is no doubt that proficiency in each skill is necessary to become a well-rounded communicator, but the ability to speak skillfully provides the speakers with several distinct advantages. The main advantages of speaking skills are:

- To participate actively in pair or group activities in the classrooms.
- To give a maiden and impressive speech on different occasions.

- To participate actively in debates and group discussions.
- To develop critical thinking among the learners.
- To pursue higher studies in foreign countries.
- To interact with people all around the globe.
- To promote the sale of products in the business.
- To make living abroad simpler and easier.
- To get better employment opportunities.
- To make use of the internet effectively.
- To perform well in job interviews.
- To acquire more knowledge.
- To travel to a foreign country.
- To do good international business.
- To earn high respect in the society.

Conclusion

In this paper, an attempt has been made to highlight the importance of speaking skills in English classrooms. First of all, the significance of the basic language skills of English has been discussed elaborately. Then, the importance of speaking skills in the EFL/ESL classrooms has been comprehensively explained. Furthermore, the need to teach speaking skills in the classrooms has been illustrated. Later on, the kinds of speaking situations and the main advantages of speaking skills have been explained sumptuously. Moreover, some techniques to develop speaking skills among the EFL/ESL learners in the classrooms have been thoroughly explained. Finally, the teachers are given some suggestions to improve speaking skills among the ELLs in the English classrooms. Also, the ELLs are also

advised to follow the guidance of their teachers in order to enhance their speaking skills. Speaking skills are the most important skills for ELLs as they are very useful for them in exhibiting their communication skills for various purposes. Hence, the teachers have to take a special interest in improving the speaking skills of the ELLS. For this purpose, the teachers have to refer to the latest material related to and try to adopt several techniques and approaches to develop the speaking skills of the learners in the English classrooms. The teachers should also choose appropriate material suitable for the level of the learners. Moreover, the teachers should encourage the learners to participate in the classroom discussions where the learners improve their speaking skills tremendously. Also, the learners have to create situations themselves to speak not only in the classroom but also outside the classroom. Furthermore, the learners have to follow the instructions of their teachers in improving their speaking skills. Since the tips given by the teachers benefit the learners, they have to implement them sincerely to communicate well at all circumstances. Therefore, the EFL/ESL teachers have to implement different strategies and techniques in their teaching in order to make their learners proficient in their speaking skills. In this regard, the ELLs have to put their whole efforts to practice speaking skills and allot more time to such activities in order to prove themselves in the contemporary world.

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